

TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH GAMES

Narimanov Shahzod Bahodir oglu¹, Absalomova Aziza Bakhodir qizi²

¹ Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, Samarkand, Uzbekistan,

² Student of Uzbek State World Languages University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received : 2021-03-05

Revised : 2021-03-08

Accepted : 2021-03-27

ABSTRACT

This article focuses on teaching foreign languages through a variety of games, increasing the effectiveness of lessons using interactive methods and games in the classroom. There is also a focus on foreign languages, especially English, and the laws that apply to them.

KEYWORDS

foreign languages

interactive, method

language level

games, law

educational standards

1. Introduction

After the independence of our country, the interest in teaching foreign languages has grown and many opportunities have been created for young people. At present, great importance is attached in our country to the teaching and learning of foreign languages. This, of course, is not in vain. Today, there is no need to underestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which are striving to take a worthy place in the world community, for our people, who are building their great future in cooperation with our foreign partners. As a logical continuation of these ideas, the Presidential Decree of December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages" expands the opportunities for learning foreign languages. The purpose of learning any foreign language is to be able to communicate fluently in that language. Teaching and learning foreign languages is a long and perfect process.

2. Method

It requires regular work and self-improvement. It is obvious that the use of various interactive

games in the process of teaching foreign languages to improve oral skills makes learning a foreign language not boring, but rather fun and enjoyable. Interactive games encourage language learners to behave more freely, even shy students. It is effective to use interactive games to increase grammar and vocabulary, especially. However, before using these games, the teacher must clearly explain to the students the purpose of the game, the rules of the game and closely relate it to the topic. The interactive games included in this set of methodological recommendations serve as a useful resource for preschool education or teaching games to schoolchildren through oral speech, on the use of games. detailed instructions are given.

Teaching has always been very important in human endeavors. This was the case even when education was random, intuitive, and consisted mainly of the transmission and imitation of information by chance; and later, when education became a purposeful, systematic and planned process, and so did the school. However, for a long time there was no theoretical analysis and study of education, so it did not have its own theory. Only the seventeenth century brought significant changes in this area: it was then that education took a special name and laid the foundation for the first scientifically based

system of didactic activity in history.

English is not boring quickly, and the learning process is not boring, in addition to teaching different skills and enriching knowledge, try to diversify its various activities. Pay attention to games to learn English in any case - if you are a teacher (skype or courses you learn with English or Tutor), and perhaps you will strive to make classes fun and memorable. Choose people like you, and play. Because it is an English learning game, you will gladly combine work.

If you are a teacher, you can invent games to learn English on their own. For example, dominoes can make puzzles, lexical material, or provide a competitive spirit for a language screen. You can only do service-game games, playing in different situations of life, using only English (seller - buyer, doctor - patient, actor - his fan, etc.). In this case, the creation or choice of games for learning English is only related to the desire to activate the imagination and the learning process. Trust me, your efforts will be appreciated and then everyone, regardless of age, likes to play big or small.

If you can't, or don't want to use tips, tricks and even ready-made materials used in games to learn English, invent something. These books and manuals are a collection of so-called materials; resource pack A lot of publications published by foreign publishers. They can be purchased or downloaded from the internet and then published what is useful to you. A great resource englishtips.org has many books on the subject: Lexical games in English classes Word Puzzles and Games (on practice and word memorization), Grammar Games (grammar checking science), Phonic games (teaching) for reading and pronunciation), Quick Thinking Games and Riddles (for developing logical thinking and ingenuity), etc. Trying to play games over and over again in the process of learning to choose games for learning English, great, but played at least once. And it would be useful.

If you are learning a language, you can also choose something that will help you to benefit from the materials mentioned above and increase your knowledge. At the same time, the most popular games Flash games are presented on the Internet, self-learning English. For example, there is a game where you have to hear a description of a person or persons, and choose the option you want. Or buy a set of goods in a

strictly allotted time. And in a way, word games are not just about numbers. If you are interested in learning English and these games, take a look at resources such as:

homeenglish.ru - you will find only a list of games links to dedicated sites in addition to the list of games probelov.net - games for learning English on various topics linguamania.ru - Game of the same name to learn English. Enter the words you want in the suggested letters and get bonuses for which you buy character clothes and accessories.

Of course, learning English only through games is not an option, but it is not only possible, but necessary to use the game in the general process of education.

3. Conclusion

In short, we can make these games easier or harder depending on the level or age of the children. The purpose of these interactive games is different, through which we can concentrate, increase vocabulary, speed, intelligence, and most importantly, learn the lesson in an interesting way and remember it. The organization of continuous learning of foreign languages at all stages of the education system, as well as the training of teachers and the provision of modern teaching materials require further improvement. By radically improving the system of teaching the younger generation in foreign languages, training specialists who are fluent in these languages through the introduction of advanced teaching methods using modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies, and on this basis, in order to create conditions and opportunities for their achievements in world civilization and the widespread use of world information resources, the development of international cooperation and dialogue: learning foreign languages throughout the country, mainly English, from the first grades of secondary schools in the form of lessons and oral speech lessons, and from the second grade onwards, the mastery of the alphabet, reading, and grammar begins step by step; Confirmation of this decision is a great way for us young people. It is a sign that great opportunities will open up for the next generation.

References

Karimov. I.A. 2012 yil 10-dekabr “Chet tiliarni o`rganish tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora tadbirlari to`g`risida”gi qarori.

Dehkanova Dilnoza “Ingliz tili darslarida interfaol o`yinlar” O`rta maxsus ta`lim bosqichi uchun o`quv-uslubiy qo`llanma. Samarqand SamDCHTI,2013 yil

“Formation of Student Aesthetic Competition by Teaching the Works of Russian Classic Composers in Music Culture Classes”

<http://www.englishclub.com/esl-activities>

<http://www.eslgamesworld.com/ClassroomGames.html>

Absalomovich N.B. Research on the use of alternative energy sources in Uzbekistan: Problems and prospects //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2020. – T. 10. – №. 11. – C. 763-768.

Yangibayevich A.A., Pardaboev A., Absalomovich N.B. Issues of modeling the perspective development of cattle breeding //South Asian Journal of Marketing & Management Research. – 2020. – T. 10. – №. 6. – C. 89-96.

Nabijonovich J.A. Renewable energy sources in Uzbekistan //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2020. – T. 10. – №. 11. – C. 769-774.